

U-ADAPT! Urban Adaptation to Extreme Heat Events

Personal data: None of the information of this section will be published and your response will be kept anonymous.

SECTION 1 OF 8: Context

E-mail*:

1. Which city are you representing?

2. What working position are you currently holding? (e.g., Head of the Resilience Department)

SECTION 2 OF 8: Evaluation of perceived Heat Disaster Risk and urban adaptation to Extreme Heat Events (EHE)

U-ADAPT approach

3. Please, list the three most concerning hazards of your city

4. Rate the current level of Heat Disaster Risk (HDR) of your city in comparison with the risk from other hazards such as drought, floods, cold waves, earthquakes, terrorism, etc.

Evaluation of U-ADAPT! objectives

Please, read the description of each of the U-ADAPT! objectives (available in the following document -LINK- and also included in the following questions as a remainder) and rate your opinion regarding its importance in terms of reducing HDR -particularly decreasing human and economic losses- and its implementation cost (human and economic resources needed for its implementation).

ADAPTATION DOMAIN	ADAPTATION GOAL	ADAPTATION OBJECTIVE
UHI effect (city scale)	G1: Reduce the amplification effect of natural heat produced by Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect	Ob.1. Reduce urban active heating: production of anthropogenic heat (waste heat)
		Ob.2. Reduce urban passive heating: absorption of natural heat
		Ob.3. Reinforcing urban cooling effect: reducing city's temperature during EHE
EHE exposure (human scale)	G2: Reduce the number of individuals and assets physically exposed to extreme heat	Ob.4. Reduce overheating in private buildings
		Ob.5. Reduce overheating in public buildings
		Ob.6. Reduce overheating of public transportation: increase passenger thermal comfort.
		Ob.7. Reduce temperature in public outdoor places (particularly those with high activity and used by vulnerable groups)
		Ob.8. Reduce heat stress of outdoor workers and attendants of mass gatherings (sport events, music festivals, etc.)
		Ob.9. Reduce time exposed to hazardous heat exposure of vulnerable populations
		Ob.10. Reduce EHE exposure of the built environment
EHE sensitivity	G3: Lessen the characteristics/features that make certain individuals and assets more susceptible when exposed to extreme heat	Ob.11. Reduce sensitivity of vulnerable groups
		Ob.12. Decrease sensitivity of the built environment and avoid infrastructure failures (also regarding future heat scenarios).
EHE coping capacity	G4: Enhance the ability of those exposed and sensitive to extreme heat of absorbing its effects and surviving the event unharmed.	Ob.13. Improve coping mechanisms and risk reduction strategies for vulnerable population
		Ob.14. Improve population awareness of EHE and safety options
		Ob.15. Enhance the capacity of monitoring and assessment
		Ob.16. Guarantee basic needs and services during heatwaves (blackouts, water shortages...)
		Ob.17. Improve EHE-specific disaster training
EHE adaptive capacity	G5: Enhance the ability of the community to adjust to reduce future exposure and sensitivity and increase their coping mechanisms	Ob.18. Increase understanding of current and future Heat Disaster Risk (HDR), past EHE effects, and potential mitigation strategies
		Ob.19. Raise HDR awareness and improving risk communication: improve education about HDR
		Ob.20. Improve the engagement of civil society, private actors, and the academia in the reduction of HDR
		Ob.21. Encourage neighbor networks and volunteering organizations (social networks) and collaboration between actors
		Ob.22. Increase the awareness of funding sources and seeking external funding

SECTION 3 OF 8: GOAL 1: Reduce the amplification effect of natural heat produced by Urban Heat Island Effect (UHI)

Ob.1. Reduce urban active heating: production of anthropogenic heat (waste heat). Anthropogenic heat, also known as waste heat or active heating, is a flux of artificial (as opposed to natural) heat derived from emissions from vehicles, industrial activities, HVAC systems, and other sources. Several authors have proposed measures and strategies to reduce anthropogenic heat, which artificially worsens the effect of natural extreme heat conditions. Banning or phasing out industrial activities in densely populated areas is one of the most efficient strategies. Cities can also promote behavioral changes among its citizens, encouraging efficient and responsible use of cooling systems -time, temperature, type of A/C, alternatives, and maintenance- and banning or disincentivizing reject heat from cooling systems from facades, balconies, and courtyards, promoting its location in the upper most roof. Transportation is another focus point in the effort to reduce waste heat. City councils could implement plans to transition from internal combustion engines to electric engines in public transportation vehicles, incentivize the migration from combustion engines in private transportation vehicles and the provisioning of charging points, promote the use of public transportation or

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sustainable transportation during heat spells -banning private transportation, making public transportation free or reducing its price, etc. Transitioning to cool lighting options (e.g., LED) in streets, parks, and other public domain places has also been suggested.

9. Rate the overall importance (relevance) of Objective 1

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Very Low	<input type="radio"/>	Very High									

10. Rate the implementation cost of Objective 1

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Very Low	<input type="radio"/>	Very High									

Ob.2. Reduce urban passive heating: absorption of natural heat. Urban passive heating relates closely with the concept of albedo (fraction of incident solar radiation diffusively reflected from a surface or body). To reduce the absorption of natural heat, urban areas have two main strategies at their disposal: the building code and urban planning. A restrictive building code could ban or phase out the use of black or dark roofs and/or require cool roofs. Urban planning could incorporate the implementation of cool paving -lighter pigments for asphalt and high Solar Reflectance Index (SRI) paving materials- and the design of urban geometries that avoid trapping heat within the city. An effective urban planning against heat should also consider compensating the total area of new building development with equivalent areas of greenery and shading paved areas (i.e., roads) wherever possible.

11. Rate the overall importance (relevance) of Objective 2

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Very Low	<input type="radio"/>	Very High									

12. Rate the implementation cost of Objective 2

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Very Low	<input type="radio"/>	Very High									

Ob.3. Reinforcing urban cooling effect: reducing city’s temperature during EHE. Bringing down the temperature of an urban area during extreme heat events (urban cooling) is feasible through a carefully designed urban planning. Urban geometries should be taken into consideration due to their effect slowing or blocking local winds and breezes. Designing green corridors or enforcing construction bans at strategic locations have been proven effective for this matter. Integrating blue infrastructure (evaporative cooling options) into the urban area such as rivers, wetlands, and other large bodies of water can temperate extreme conditions. Alongside with urban planning, urban forestry regulations and the development of parks, gardens, woodland, etc. can maximize the evapotranspiration cooling effect, for which urban farming and gardening

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also plays an important role. In addition, removing paving and/or increasing pervious surfaces or increasing the use of more permeable paving materials is also a recommended measure.

13. Rate the overall importance (relevance) of Objective 3

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Very Low	<input type="radio"/>	Very High									

14. Rate the implementation cost of Objective 3

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Very Low	<input type="radio"/>	Very High									

SECTION 4 OF 8: GOAL 2: Reduce the number of individuals and assets physically exposed to extreme heat

Ob.4. Reduce overheating in private buildings. The building code is again an essential ally to reduce HDR as it is able to enforce an appropriate building/house design for the city’s climate -materials, shading, interior design, natural ventilation, etc.- and impose standards for appropriate building/house retrofitting including better insulation and passive designs with special attention to building envelopes. City councils might also incentive (including but not limited to credit, rebates, tax deductions, free labor, and fee waivers) the installation of air conditioning -in certain buildings-, cool roofs/walls/facades, vertical planting and green roofs, shading devices, and more efficient heat-generating home appliances -e.g., lights, oven, stoves, fridge. Incentivized inspections by a thermal performance assessor or energy auditors have also been suggested. Other measures such as implementing stricter requirements to locate A/C units away from adjacent properties to minimize heat transfer or making summertime -or heatwave- noise threshold limits more stringent to allow neighbors to open their windows at night are also on the table in some urban areas.

15. Rate the overall importance (relevance) of Objective 4

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Very Low	<input type="radio"/>	Very High									

16. Rate the implementation cost of Objective 4

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Very Low	<input type="radio"/>	Very High									

Ob.5. Reduce overheating in public buildings. Within public constructions of their jurisdiction, city councils can explore the installation of air conditioning in certain buildings -schools, prisons, hospitals, care homes, etc.- and similar measures and strategies applied to private buildings such as cool coatings in roofs, walls, and facades, installing vertical planting and green roofs, shading devices, or following extreme heat standards for correct building retrofitting.

17. Rate the overall importance (relevance) of Objective 5

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low Very High

18. Rate the implementation cost of Objective 5

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low Very High

Ob.6. Reduce overheating of public transportation: increase passenger thermal comfort. Public transportation is another source of citizen’s heat stress. In this matter, cities could implement plans and standards to improve powertrains and subway lines efficiency -e.g., lowering subway car weighs- to reduce waste heat that transfers into wagons and stations or improving bus efficiency -e.g., transitioning to electric vehicles. Installing efficient mechanical cooling systems on buses and trains, exploring alternative cooling systems such as pumped groundwater for stations, transitioning to cool lighting options -LED- within the subway and buses, and more ambitious plans to remove excess heat from subway tunnels -e.g., Ground Source Heat Exchangers, regenerative braking systems, ventilation- and opening up subway stations to increase natural light and air circulation have also been discussed. The simple installation of fans and/or misting systems at bus stops or subway stations are also implemented in some cities.

19. Rate the overall importance (relevance) of Objective 6

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low Very High

20. Rate the implementation cost of Objective 6

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low Very High

Ob.7. Reduce temperature in public outdoor places (particularly those with high activity and used by vulnerable groups). Urban planning can also reduce air temperature at the local (human) scale by paying attention to the orientation of site features -preferably northern and eastern side of buildings-, implementing permeable paving and cool surfaces in pedestrian areas, designing contiguous canopy coverage (dense trees) in main streets and parks, incorporating evaporative cooling with accommodating ponds, pools, fountains, sprinklers and misting systems, and increasing evapotranspiration by providing irrigation to landscaped areas. The installation of shading devices in main pedestrian areas is also a widely used measure. Restrictions such as vehicle circulation and avoiding heat exhaust from HVAC systems in pedestrian areas – encouraging heat rejection from the roof- are additional effective strategies.

21. Rate the overall importance (relevance) of Objective 7

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1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

22. Rate the implementation cost of Objective 7

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

Ob.8. Reduce heat stress of outdoor workers and attendants of mass gatherings (sport events, music festivals, etc.). Avoiding heat extreme conditions for those regularly or occasionally exposed to inclement weather is possible for cities following several strategies. Requiring the installation of portable shading devices, portable fans and misting systems, and drinking fountains are seen as effective mechanisms to ameliorate heat stress. However, during the most extreme conditions, banning non-essential outdoor work or prohibiting outdoor mass gatherings are the most effective measures to reduce HDR.

23. Rate the overall importance (relevance) of Objective 8

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

24. Rate the implementation cost of Objective 8

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

Ob.9. Reduce time exposed to hazardous heat exposure of vulnerable populations. The literature identifies certain subpopulations with higher vulnerability to climate variability and extremes. Children, elderly, women, socially isolated individuals, chronically ill, overweight people, top-floor apartment residents, persons with mental/physical impairments, homeless, outdoor workers, drug/alcohol addicts, tourists, or Muslims during Ramadan are some of the most referenced groups. City councils might encourage remote working during heatwaves (or summertime) for vulnerable individuals or mandate more regular breaks. Adaptive work schedules and modifying the visiting schedule and times of touristic attractions (e.g., allowing night visits) during heatwaves or the summertime.

25. Rate the overall importance (relevance) of Objective 9

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

26. Rate the implementation cost of Objective 9

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1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

Ob.10. Reduce EHE exposure of the built environment. Locating the built environment away from the heat is often a challenging task, but cities must consider placing vulnerable infrastructure in non-exposed locations. For instance, the Secretary of State for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs of the United Kingdom suggested locating main power transformers underground or in shaded or north-oriented areas and placing power and ICT cabling underground to adapt to present and future threats of climate change.

27. Rate the overall importance (relevance) of Objective 10

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

28. Rate the implementation cost of Objective 10

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

SECTION 5 OF 8: GOAL 3: Lessen the characteristics/features that make certain individuals and assets more susceptible when exposed to extreme heat

Ob.11. Reduce sensitivity of vulnerable groups. As explained earlier, several subpopulations have a higher susceptibility to being harmed during extreme heat. However, altering the intrinsic characteristics and features that make them vulnerable is challenging or unreasonable. Some of the characteristics that could be improved relates to the lifestyle and social relationships. Thus, city governments could promote healthy lifestyles -particularly but not limited to the elderly- by offering discounts in municipal pools, gyms, or sport centers. Promoting home sharing among the elderly to prevent social isolation is also a useful mechanism to reduce elderly sensitivity. Tackling homelessness by developing programs and allocating resources to offer housing alternatives and sources of income to homeless reduces their overall vulnerability and their sensitivity to extreme heat.

29. Rate the overall importance (relevance) of Objective 11

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

30. Rate the implementation cost of Objective 11

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

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Ob.12. Decrease sensitivity of the built environment and avoid infrastructure failures (also regarding future heat scenarios). Altering the characteristics that make the built environment sensitive is a more feasible task. Power, roads, and railways are within the most affected infrastructure by extreme heat. City councils could invest in decentralized energy generation (i.e., localized microgeneration) to improve reliability of power in stressed conditions, protect power transformers from overheating by avoiding steel, providing shading and better insulation, or increasing its albedo, and strengthen power cable to avoid excess wire expansion -sagging lines. Carrying out evaluation assessments of transformer performances under high loads (electricity) demands has also been proven important. Not much has been tried to prevent railway buckling (sun kinks) other than painting tracks with light colors to increase albedo, ensuring a thorough maintenance of the railway network or increasing construction standards to lessen buckling. Regarding roads, again, maintenance and more stringent climate-proofed standards should be implemented, paying attention to heat-resistant materials for roads and the possibility of cool pavements.

31. Rate the overall importance (relevance) of Objective 12

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Very Low	<input type="radio"/>	Very High									

32. Rate the implementation cost of Objective 12

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Very Low	<input type="radio"/>	Very High									

SECTION 6 OF 8: GOAL 4: Enhance the ability of those exposed and sensitive to extreme heat to absorb its effects and surviving the event unharmed.

Ob.13. Improve coping mechanisms and risk reduction strategies for vulnerable population. Measures following this objective have likely been the most widely adopted by city councils to reduce HDR. Literature is therefore rich in examples of measures taken during heatwaves such as opening up cooling centers and shelters -even offering evacuations for the physically impaired, establishing telephone help-lines or hotlines, implementing programs to actively check on vulnerable groups - i.e., elderly, homeless, chronically ill, making indoor and outdoor pools free or low-price and extending operation hours, promoting the relaxation of the dressing code, banning outside class recess and outdoor physical activities for children, offering water bottle and hand fan giveaways at touristic attractions, developing programs so citizens check in on at-risk neighbors, making available emergency substance withdrawal kits for drugs and alcohol addicts, and enforcing mandatory cooling brakes for outdoor workers.

33. Rate the overall importance (relevance) of Objective 13

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Very Low	<input type="radio"/>	Very High									

34. Rate the implementation cost of Objective 13

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1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

Ob.14. Improve population awareness of EHE and safety options. Making citizens aware of the danger of a specific EHE (as opposed to general HDR awareness of Ob. 19) and safety options is basic to guarantee their wellbeing. In this regard, authors have suggested launching information campaigns with regular announcements, ad-hoc bulletins or webpages, billboards, or leaflets in several languages about the danger of the EHE, releasing media (TV, radio, social media, journals, etc.) announcements about upcoming and current heatwaves, or promoting outreach to inform the homeless population of HDR and available protection. Others describe more directly targeted measures such as active emergency alerts to cellphones through SMS or mobile applications), email, phone call, or in person visits. Communication with at-risk groups should also be improved. Some have pointed out the need to improve HDR information for Muslims fasting during Ramadan, which could be done at mosques or halal butcher’s shops, increase outreach among high-risk areas and top floor apartment dwellers, and improve HDR information in addiction and rehabilitation centers and by social services. Encouraging medical providers to inform certain patients (such as the elderly, the chronically ill, and pregnant women) about the danger of extreme heat could be also an adopted measure.

35. Rate the overall importance (relevance) of Objective 14

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

36. Rate the implementation cost of Objective 14

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

Ob.15. Enhance the capacity of monitoring and assessment. Improving the city’s real-time monitoring and assessment capacity needs to be considered. This could be achieved by establishing early heat/health watches and warning systems, reinforcing the air quality monitoring and alert mechanisms, instituting early-warning systems for increased hospital admissions and mortality, and extending the urban temperature monitoring network -meteorological stations. Creating a regularly updated database of vulnerable groups and a map of heatwave vulnerability is also a measure adopted in some urban areas.

37. Rate the overall importance (relevance) of Objective 15

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

38. Rate the implementation cost of Objective 15

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1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

Ob.16. Guarantee basic needs and services during heatwaves (blackouts, water shortages...).

Access to both electricity and water is essential for any human being, and both can be challenged during an EHE. Cities can adopt measures to guarantee these services under extreme circumstances such as building or incentivizing in-grid micro-generation facilities and large-capacity batteries (e.g., rooftop solar power generation) that increases the city’s power capacity to meet peak demands and avoids total power outages. Prohibiting water and electricity companies to disconnect citizens from the services for non-payment during heatwaves, encouraging responsible use of non-essential appliances (dishwasher, washing machine, etc.) during the peak hours of electricity demand during an EHE, or implementing subsidies for low-income households to support paying the electricity bill for cooling needs.

39. Rate the overall importance (relevance) of Objective 16

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

40. Rate the implementation cost of Objective 16

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

Ob.17. Improve EHE-specific disaster training. EHEs can rapidly escalate into a major disaster and cause multiple cascading effects such as blackouts/power outages, water shortages, or civil unrest. EHE emergency planning must be considered by cities -including the aforementioned cascading effects- and implement specific staff training (drills), planification for the health and social care systems under stressed conditions, and community and private sector preparedness and training for the worst circumstances.

41. Rate the overall importance (relevance) of Objective 17

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

42. Rate the implementation cost of Objective 17

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

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SECTION 7 OF 8: GOAL 5: Enhance the ability of the community to adjust to reduce future exposure and sensitivity and increase their coping mechanisms.

Ob.18. Increase understanding of current and future Heat Disaster Risk (HDR), past EHE effects, and potential mitigation strategies. Increasing the understanding of current and future HDR, past EHE effects, and potential mitigation strategies is essential for successful adaptation. Many measures and strategies can relate to this objective, but one of the first steps for cities must be the creation of a Resilience Office or an Adaptation Office with affiliated staff. Requiring sectorial risk assessment incorporating climate change projections and heat mitigation plans for outdoor working sites, the subway, hospital, schools, prisons etc. Analyzing the excess mortality of past EHE within the urban area and the effects in the built environment are necessary steps to fully understand the implications of EHE in the local scale. Cities should also investigate and evaluate the response from different stakeholders to past events and encourage participatory learning, fund city-specific research about HDR and its mitigation, and participating in pilot and demonstration HDR reduction projects.

43. Rate the overall importance (relevance) of Objective 18

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Very Low	<input type="radio"/>	Very High									

44. Rate the implementation cost of Objective 18

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Very Low	<input type="radio"/>	Very High									

Ob.19. Raise HDR awareness and improving risk communication: improve education about HDR. Increasing citizens' HDR awareness and improving risk communication is vital to create the required environment to spur adaptation. Building partnerships and enhancing coordination between the local government and relevant public/private stakeholders such as schools, senior centers, or health providers to educate their administrative teams, professionals, and staff about HDR is one of the most effective strategies. Another partnership worth to explore and expand is with the media, particularly health and weather reporters, who could benefit from workshops and training sessions dedicated to properly communicate HDR and other environmental threats. Another measures in line with this objective are the organization of extreme heat awareness and preparedness week/day that stimulate behavioral change towards HDR and the evaluation and assessment of the effectiveness of past risk communication efforts.

45. Rate the overall importance (relevance) of Objective 19

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Very Low	<input type="radio"/>	Very High									

46. Rate the implementation cost of Objective 19

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1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

Ob.20. Improve the engagement of civil society, private actors, and the academia in the reduction

of HDR. Making stakeholders participants of the HDR reduction process through its engagement the in planning and implementation phases is crucial to assure the success of the adaptation process. Identifying community key leaders, the business sector, emergency responders, relevant local academics, community-based organizations, non-governmental organizations, faith-based organizations, and media outlets is one of the first steps to take. Then, maintaining and offering communication channels (meetings, workshops, participatory web portals...) permits finding coalitions and synergies among stakeholders to reduce HDR.

47. Rate the overall importance (relevance) of Objective 20

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

48. Rate the implementation cost of Objective 20

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

Ob.21. Encourage neighbor networks and volunteering organizations (social networks) and collaboration between actors.

To provide a thriving and prosper environment for social networks such as neighbor and volunteering organizations to emerge and collaborate in HDR reduction city councils could create a Civic Engagement and Volunteer Service Office and fund or incentive neighbor and volunteering organizations. Other measures and strategies could involve offering training and technological support for social networks or individually incentivizing and recognizing social network participants through tax deductions, discounts, or free events.

49. Rate the overall importance (relevance) of Objective 21

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

50. Rate the implementation cost of Objective 21

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low

Very High

Ob.22. Increase the awareness of funding sources and seeking external funding.

Facilitate access to funding sources for HDR reduction for businesses and citizens is essential to provide the needed resources for adaptation. Developing a website or portal that gathers the adaptation incentives offered by organizations

and different levels of government could be very beneficial. City officials should also search for coalitions with the banking sector to offer low-interest rates in loans for adapting to climate change and actively explore national and international funding programs dedicated to urban adaptation.

51. Rate the overall importance (relevance) of Objective 22

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low Very High

52. Rate the implementation cost of Objective 22

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Very Low Very High

SECTION 8 OF 8: State your opinion!

53. Please, if you like, use this space to comment on the project, add any kind of suggestion, formulate questions or share experiences you think it could be of interest for U-ADAPT!

Thank you for your time and attention.

Your response is highly appreciated